

Stroke Monitoring System using The Microwave Imaging System

(Sistem Pemantauan Strok Menggunakan Sistem Pengimejan Gelombang Mikro)

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ABSTRACT

Stroke or known as brain attack is a disease that is becoming more prevalent now after a heart attack. Stroke is a serious injury to the brain that can cause fatal. Computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are the introduced machines in line with technological advances in the field of medicine, but they were inefficient in terms of radiation generation that endangered the patients and impractical large size. The operating costs for both are high and not suitable for continuous monitoring sessions especially for the underprivileged. Thus, microwave imaging technology emerged as a user-friendly technology. Low cost, medium size, portable, safe and its waves are able to penetrate the tissue layers are among the advantages of microwave technology. This study aims to develop a stroke monitoring system that is more effective than existing systems as well as evaluate and validate the performance of the system. A 3D antenna model of a folded structure with a PEC type wall with dimensions of $70 \times 30 \times 14 \text{ mm}^3$ is modelled in a CST Microwave Studio 2019 with frequency operation of 1-3 GHz. The Hugo head model, hemorrhagic stroke elements and nine antenna array elements were integrated in the simulator. The obtained scattering parameters were collected and then analyzed for image reconstruction process using existing algorithms. The antenna showed a consistent directional radiation with the gain of 5.31 dBi and the simulations on the nine elements of the antenna array showed the reflection coefficients for the transmitter antenna and the receiver antenna are below -10 dB and -20 dB, respectively. The image formed is clear and sharp because the noise interference obtained is minimal. Overall, the developed system has the capability in detecting hemorrhagic stroke accurately in the head phantom model by using a microwave system.

Keywords: Haemorrhagic; microwave imaging; image reconstruction

ABSTRAK

Strok ataupun serangan otak adalah penyakit yang makin berleluasa kini selepas serangan jantung. Strok merupakan kecederaan serius pada otak yang boleh membawa maut. Tomografi berkomputer (CT) dan pengimejan resonans magnetik (MRI) adalah mesin yang diperkenalkan selaras dengan kemajuan teknologi dalam bidang perubatan tetapi ia tidak efisien dari penghasilan radiasinya yang membahayakan pengguna dan saiz besar yang tidak praktikal. Malah kos operasi untuk keduanya adalah tinggi dan tidak sesuai untuk sesi pemantauan yang berterusan terutamanya bagi golongan yang tidak berkemampuan. Oleh itu, teknologi pengimejan gelombang mikro muncul sebagai sebuah teknologi mesra pengguna. Berkos rendah, bersaiz sederhana, mudah alih, selamat dan gelombangnya mampu menembusi lapisan tisu adalah antara kelebihan teknologi gelombang mikro. Kajian ini bertujuan untuk membangunkan sistem pemantauan strok yang lebih efektif daripada sistem yang sedia ada kemudian menilai dan mengesahkan prestasi sistem. Model antena 3D struktur berlipat bersama dinding jenis PEC berdimensi $70 \times 30 \times 14 \text{ mm}^3$ dibangunkan di dalam pensimulasi CST 2019 dengan operasi frekuensi 1-3 GHz. Model fantom kepala Hugo, elemen strok hemoragik dan sembilan elemen tatasusunan antena disatukan di dalam simulator. Parameter serakan yang diperolehi dikumpul kemudian dianalisis untuk proses pembentukan semula imej dengan menggunakan algoritma sedia ada. Antena menunjukkan kriteria arah radiasi yang konsisten dengan nilai gandaan sebanyak 5.31 dBi dan simulasi pada sembilan elemen tatasusunan antena menunjukkan pekali pantulan untuk antena pemancar dan antena penerima masing-masing di bawah -10 dB dan -20 dB. Imej yang terbentuk adalah jelas dan tajam kerana gangguan hingar yang diperolehi adalah minimal. Keseluruhannya, sistem yang dibangunkan mempunyai keupayaan dalam mengesan strok hemoragik dengan tepat dan jelas didalam model fantom kepala dengan menggunakan sistem gelombang mikro.

Kata Kunci: Hemoragik; pengimejan gelombang mikro; pembentukan semula imej

INTRODUCTION

Older age, diabetes, high cholesterol, high blood pressure and atrial fibrillation are among the factors the risk of stroke attack its prey. A stroke occurs when the blood flow to a part of the brain is interrupted. Blood flow is interrupted when the blood vessels in the head clogged or broken. Without a blood supply, brain cells can be damaged. Ischemic and hemorrhagic as shown in Figure 1 are the typical types of strokes. The cause of ischemic stroke is a blood clot in the arteries that supply blood to the brain, whereas the cause of hemorrhagic stroke is a rupturing of a blood vessel, resulting in bleeding and increased pressure in the brain. Stroke can be fatal or permanent disability problems if not treated promptly.

For the treatment and rehabilitation of patients, an effective diagnosis is crucial. Thus, head imaging is a critical component in ensuring the affected patient's recovery through timely treatment and on-the-spot detection. In medical diagnostic imaging system, now doctors rely on the system more advanced diagnostic devices such as Computed Tomography (CT) scans and Magnetic Resonance Monitoring Imaging (MRI) for diagnostic and examination purposes (Sohani et al. 2019). However, they are costly, expose patients to dangerous radiation, difficult to access in remote areas, and not affordable to everyone. The size of existing imaging devices makes it difficult for pandemic teams to transport them to specified locations for diagnosis purposes.

Nowadays, microwave technology is the main focus research in medical imaging applications. It has a variety of positive criteria among them, the non-ionized radiation, which is safe at any ages, affordable cost, medium size and portable. Microwave-based imaging is different when compared to techniques traditional imaging i.e., CT scans and MRI. The MWI technique is about detecting differences in the dielectric properties of healthy tissue and diseased tissue.

This technique is safer compared to the use of ionizing radiation which can endanger the patient.

FIGURE 1: Ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke
Source: (Tan 2019)

The use of wideband EM imaging in the diagnosis of breast cancer and the detection of brain damage has become commonplace. The antenna is the most important part of the EM head imaging system. The antenna array sends out a low-level EM signal in the direction of the human head. Then the scattered signal is collected and processed using a variety of algorithms in order to reconstruct the interior of the human head and pinpoint the injuries. To detect and recreate the images, the variations in electrical properties between normal and diseased heads are used.

Many studies in the past literature focus on system performance on detecting the stroke. Table 1 shows six studies with different objectives conducted on the interaction between the system and the type of stroke detection. Based on Table 1, the type of hemorrhagic stroke is the component that frequently studied by the researcher. Only three studies were carried out on the ischemic stroke According to Table 1, these studies are related to different dielectric properties between the healthy head tissue and dielectric properties of ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke.

TABLE 1: Investigation on system interaction

No	Reference	Stroke Elements	
		Ischemic	Haemorrhagic
1	Karadima et al. (2020)	x	x
2	Pokorny et al. (2019)	x	x
3	Merunka et al. (2019)		x
4	Scapatucci et al. (2018)		x
5	Hopfer et al. (2017)	x	x
6	Bialkowski & Ireland (2011)		x

Stroke can be detected when there is a difference in dielectric between damaged tissue and normal human head tissue. Stroke is a blood vessel disorder that can cause damage to tissues. Thus,

stroke will be detected through the tissue damage produced. In terms of antenna setup and image reconstruction, researchers are now proposing numerous techniques for EM head imaging. Sohani

et al. (2020) shows a triangular patch antenna with two antenna array elements for obtaining the scattering signals that limit the ability to reconstruct images. While Alqadami et al. (2020) describes a flexible antenna for EM head imaging that concentrates primarily on scattering parameters and fidelity factor rather than image reconstruction, a head phantom with tissue mimicry is required to confirm antenna performance. Algorithm for ICH image detection presented in Mobashsher et al. (2016) is not well detected even though data acquisition process is quite fast. Following various studies conducted by researchers, many weaknesses have been identified.

In UKM the research on head imaging system have been conducted on prototype and computerized simulators. Previous research by Hossain et al. (2020) conducted shows the simulation analysis on the head model and it focuses on scattering parameters and performance factors of the antenna model compared to the formation stroke image. Low gain and inconsistent radiation direction at the antenna causing the performance and capabilities of existing systems to decrease. Low gain due to high energy loss during signal reflection occurs as well as the influence of the antenna model structure. This limitation causes stroke detection in the head will be disrupted and improvements on the model antennas need to be done to increase the effectiveness of head imaging systems.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the capabilities of the antenna model on stroke detection. The antenna model developed by modification from the existing antenna model and research paper from Hossain et al. (2020) and Shahidul Islam et al. (2021) are referred. Besides, it also aims to detect stroke's location accurately and to obtain the image reconstruction using the existing algorithm more clearly. Basically, this paper is about the performance evaluation of a system modeled in a computer simulation by detect stroke more effectively.

METHODOLOGY

Antenna Design

The single antenna modeled is a 3D type antenna with PEC type walls on both sides and bottom of the antenna. The optimum dimensions of a single antenna are $70 \times 30 \times 14 \text{ mm}^3$ and 1.57 mm thickness of Rogers RT5880 is used as an antenna substrate where the relative permittivity and loss tangent of the material is 2.2 and 0.0009, respectively. The antenna patch and ground have same dimension which is responsible to control the high resonant frequencies of the antenna. The antenna model and its parameter are shown in Figure 2 and Table 2. The antenna's properties are

designed and analyzed using CST, a frequency domain-based EM simulator software.

Nine elements antenna array of a circle - configured modeled using the same nine single antennas as developed in Figure 3. The coordinates and the distance between the antennas should be thoroughly scrutinized as it gives effect on simulation. The angle of each antenna is 40° to form round structured antenna array.

FIGURE 2: Antenna model (a) front view, (b) bottom view and (c) perspective view

TABLE 2: Antenna parameter

Parameter	Size(mm)	Parameter	Size(mm)
W	30	L_8	9
L	70	L_9	11
L_1	5	L_{10}	4.2
L_2	3.5	L_{11}	7.5
L_3	9	L_{12}	3.38
L_4	5.5	L_{13}	3
L_5	20	L_{14}	10
L_6	25	H	14
L_7	4		

FIGURE 3: Nine elements antenna array

Head Phantom Model and Hemorrhagic Element

The human head has several layers such as skin, fat, skull, gray matter, white matter, CSF, and blood (hemorrhagic stroke). Each element has their own tissue layer thickness, dielectric properties, and electrical conduction. Developing the Hugo head phantom model must have the properties and criteria that similar to a real human head. This is to analyze the antenna performances and test its effectiveness to detect hemorrhagic stroke in the head human. To obtain the dielectric accuracy and thickness of the tissue layer, analysis of several men head at various ages was carried out. The result, thickness tissue for the skin is from 0.5-1.5 mm and the skull is 3-11 mm. The dielectric properties of head tissues are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3: Dielectric of head tissues

Tissue type	Relative permittivity (ϵ_r)	Conductivity (S/m)
Fat	5.46	0.051
Skull	12.45	0.143
Skin	43.75	0.856
CSF	68.64	2.413
Gray Matter	52.73	0.942
White Matter	38.89	0.591
Blood	61.36	1.538
Hemorrhagic	68.0	5.34

Six layers of tissue of Hugo head phantom with radius of 100 mm placed at the center of the antenna array with the distance between the arrangement of the antennas and the layer of skin tissue is 15 mm as shown in Figure 4.

The nine-element antenna array of 3D antenna, Hugo head phantom model and hemorrhagic stroke element were combined and developed into CST Suite Studio 2019 software for further analysis. Thus Figure 5 shows the flowchart of the whole system operation.

FIGURE 4: Cross section of head model
Source: (Hossain et al. 2020)

FIGURE 5: Flowchart of the whole system operation

From the flowchart given in Figure 5, the analyzing process occur when the result of the simulation has been done on the CST. The gain, s-parameter and reflection coefficient are be observed and recorded. The best antenna performance should produce a gain value higher than 4 dBi, radiation should be directional, and the reflective coefficient of s-parameter must below than -10 dB. Otherwise, it will affect the result

because while analyzing the data it may show nothing or very high distortion and will facing the difficulties on imaging process. Two conditions of Hugo head phantom model are tested to obtain the capability of antenna to penetrate the tissue layers and hemorrhagic stroke.

Image reconstruction

The images are reconstructed using a modified delay and sum technique. This existing IC-CF-DMAS algorithm are tested, and it gives the high resolution of image, low noise on image reconstruction, stroke detection is accurate, sharp and clear. The flow of the reconstruct image is shown in Figure 6.

Simulation result for s-parameter of nine elements antenna array is used for the analysis of microwave signal contrast and to construct the image. The magnitude and phase of the antennas are collected by using one antenna transmitter and other eight as receivers. The resulting s-parameter from antenna array simulation divided into two namely S_{odd} and S_{even} . The Inverse Fourier Transform is then used to transform the S_{odd} signal into time-domain mode. After that, the time domain signal is processed to reconstruct the images by applying the IC-CF-DMAS algorithm. The delay

signal is produced by getting signal from transmitting antenna and receiving antenna in the antenna array. Numerical data is received as algorithm output, then the data is transport into OriginPRO software to develop the image of the head.

Testing and validation

Three sets of image reconstruction scenario were used in the system for testing and validation. The imaging on clear head without any stroke element is the first set, and this can be used to determine the imaging area covered by the developed model. Second one is the image on the head model with element stroke, this is to determine the location of the stroke in the head. The third set is the image on the head model with stroke element. This is to determine the antenna performance and radiation while detecting the hemorrhagic stroke accurately. The three sets of imaging compared and concluded.

There are two contour graphs that have been generated, one for the head model without stroke and the other for the head model with stroke. Both graphs are compared to make sure if the bleeding has been captured at its exact location.

FIGURE 6: The flow of image reconstruction

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Antenna Analysis

The antenna is modelled using the given parameter in Table 2. Several references are used as the comparison on antenna performance. The antenna is developed by the modification on the existing antenna prototype in UKM. The analysis is done by running the simulation using the CST Microwave Suite 2019.

The response of the scattering parameter or known as the s-parameter is a measure reflected energy and radiated energy in microwave filters. It is measured by a VNA is connected to the developed system model. VNA able to separate the emitted and reflected energy using a directed coupler for the measure of power. Generally, s-parameter is used to identify the operating frequency of antenna. The operating frequency has been optimized to be 1 GHz to 3 GHz. It is determined by the frequency range in which the antenna operates when the signal level falls below -10 dB, which means that only 10% of the input power is reflected by the antenna, and the rest is delivered completely.

FIGURE 7: Scattering parameter

The scattering parameter of the antenna which is represented in Figure 7 shows the reflective coefficient under -10 dB and the highest scattering parameter is -46.12 dB at 2.55 GHz. The antenna functions in the frequency range of 1.58 GHz to 2.74 GHz, according to the simulation.

Next is the simulating the gain of the antenna and realized gain are presented in Figure 8. The term "realized gain" refers to a gain calculation that includes losses due to reflection and losses due to the antenna structure. The simulated on the antenna design shows the maximum gain of 5.31 dBi at 2.6 GHz.

The 3D radiation pattern is analyzed with far field radiation characteristic at 1.94 GHz and 5.55 GHz respectively. The simulated result shown in Figure 9. The antenna exhibits a consistent

directional radiation characteristic at the specified frequencies, with an average gain of 4.92 dBi.

FIGURE 8: Realized gain

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 9: 3D radiation pattern

Head model and stroke element analysis

The Hugo head phantom is developed according to the parameters set in Table 3, then hemorrhagic stroke is developed in spherical shape with radius of 15 mm, placed inside the head phantom to test the radiation level of the antenna in detecting stroke. A single antenna is positioned at a 90° angle from the head model's center.

The analysis is carried out on the antenna scattering parameters on the two conditions of head model which is with or without the stroke element. A single antenna's scattering parameter that is 15 mm away from the head model is presented in Figure 10. The simulation s-parameter for both

condition of head models shows the reflective coefficient continuously remain below -10 dB but different in reflection coefficient value and frequency value.

The reflection coefficient value of head model with stroke is -45.2 dB at 1.92 GHz while the reflection coefficient of model without stroke is -32.6 dB at 2 GHz. So, the head model with stroke gives the lowest reflection coefficient at the lowest frequency.

FIGURE 10: Scattering parameter on head model (a) without stroke and (b) with stroke

Figure 11 represents the setup of nine elements of antenna array with their scattering parameter. The first antenna is a transmitter while the other eight are receiver. The scattering parameter shows the reflective coefficient for both transmitting and receiving antenna are remain below -10 dB and -20 dB respectively.

FIGURE 11: Nine element antenna setup with (a) perspective view and (b) scattering parameter

Image reconstruction analysis

Three sets of image reconstruction have been executed for analysis on system model validation. The flow of reconstructing the image has been followed as Figure 6.

Figure 12 represents the first imaging set of clear head without any stroke element. It is observed that the whole contour graph is filled with blue color while the green contour indicates as the antenna radiation in the head model.

FIGURE 12: Contour graph without stroke element

Figure 13 represents the contour graph with stroke element as mentioned as imaging set two and three. Two different antenna position is placed to test the validation of system model on detecting stroke. The highest contour on the image is shown as the stroke detection. The rectangular red mark shows the hemorrhagic detection on their exact location.

Two different antenna location is the changes of transmitter antenna location in the system. Original location is at the origin of the clockwise rotation while the changes of transmitter antenna is at 180° of the clockwise rotation. The different radiation observed on the contour graph of how the antenna radiated to detect stroke element.

The stroke is detected clearly with the highest color contour in the graph.

FIGURE 13: Contour graph with element stroke (a) original antenna location and (b) different antenna location

CONCLUSION

The model of stroke monitoring system is presented using $70 \times 30 \times 14 \text{ mm}^3$ dimensions of 3D antenna type with folded structured. The design of the patch and ground in same dimension, which is to enhance the antenna performance in directionality, gain and accurately in imaging. The antenna model achieves realized gain of 5.31 dBi, within the frequency range 1 GHz to 3 GHz, also achieving stable performances. Besides, the antenna also gives the stable far field radiation pattern within the stated operational frequency. The nine elements of antenna array, dielectric constant of head tissues and hemorrhagic stroke, algorithms, and post-processing of the scattered signals are the main components to the head imaging system. The 3D antenna is validated by using it with a head model phantom and using the IC-CF-DMAS technique to reconstruct the image and immediately detect the hemorrhagic stroke. The location of the stroke was determined by the highest contour in the

imaging graph. The stroke location is identified since the executed images are brighter and sharper in color. As a result of the reconstructed images, the system model appears to be a potential strategy for detecting the early stage of brain hemorrhages in a portable EM imaging system for the head.

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